

HYDTRENCH

- **HYDFDR**
- HYDCALC
- HYDPFL

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HYDFDR

Abstract:

This software analyzes an exfiltration trench for various methods, ambient conditions, and storm parameters. The user has the ability to analyze his design and perform flood routing calculations in order to evaluate the capacity of the exfiltration trench.

This software can be downloaded through the link below,

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/jf8vsmhhq013mdd/AACJfnUjpiiCieTCusBS0JxEa?dl=0>

FRENCH DRAIN ANALYSIS

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FRENCH DRAIN ANALYSIS

1.0 DESCRIPTION

The HYDFDR program was developed as a tool to help engineers quickly analyze exfiltration trenches, better known as “French Drains”, for various methods, ambient conditions, and storm parameters.

2.0 UNITS

HYDFDR is a dimensionless based program. It analyses an exfiltration trench in either the Metric, or the English units.

3.0 ANALYSIS METHOD

This program performs the hydrologic analysis of an exfiltration trench using five different methods. They are:

1. The Rational-Critical Storm.
2. The FDOT-Modified Rational.
3. The SCS-Santa Barbara.
4. The SCS-Design Storm.
5. The SCS-Flood Hydrograph.

These methods will be elaborated further in the routing section.

4.0 DRAINAGE AREAS AND RUNOFF COEFFICIENTS

Three areas are allowed as input. They could be entered either in Acres (English units) or Hectares (Metric units). In addition, depending on the method used, a runoff coefficient characteristic of the land usage must be entered. For the “Rational-Critical Storm”, and the “FDOT-Modified Rational”, it is the rational coefficient “C”. While for the “SCS-Santa Barbara”, the “SCS-Design Storm”, and the “SCS-Flood Hydrograph” it is the curve number “CN”.

Table 1: Runoff Coefficients for the Rational Method and a 5 to 10 year Frequencies

Description of Area	Range of Runoff Coefficients	Recommended Value
Business		
Downtown	0.70-0.95	0.85
Neighborhood	0.50-0.70	0.60
Residential		
Single family	0.30-0.50	0.40
Multiunit detached	0.40-0.60	0.50
Multiunit attached	0.60-0.75	0.70
Residential (suburban)	0.25-0.40	0.35
Apartment	0.50-0.70	0.60
Industrial		
Light	0.50-0.80	0.65
Heavy	0.60-0.90	0.75
Parks, cemeteries	0.10-0.25	0.20
Playgrounds	0.20-0.35	0.30
Railroad yard	0.20-0.35	0.30
Unimproved	0.10-0.30	0.20
Character of Surface	Range of Runoff Coefficients	Recommended Value
Pavement		
Asphalt and Concrete	0.70-0.95	0.85
Brick	0.75-0.85	0.80
Roofs	0.75-0.95	0.85
Lawns, sandy soil		
Flat, 2%	0.05-0.10	0.08
Average, 2 to 7%	0.10-0.15	0.13
Steep, 7%	0.15-0.20	0.18
Lawns, heavy soil		
Flat, 2%	0.13-0.17	0.15
Average, 2 to 7%	0.18-0.22	0.20
Steep, 7%	0.25-0.35	0.30

Source: *Design and Construction of Sanitary and Storm Sewers*, American Society of Civil Engineers, New York, p. 332, 1969.

Table 2: Curve Numbers for Urban Land Uses ($I_a=0.2S$)

Land Use Description	Curve Numbers for Hydrologic Soil Group			
	A	B	C	D
Fully developed urban areas (vegetation established)				
Lawns, open spaces, parks, golf courses, cemeteries, etc.				
Good condition; grass cover >75% of the area	39	61	74	80
Fair condition; grass cover >50% to 75% of the area	49	69	79	84
Poor condition; grass cover <50% of the area	68	79	86	89
Paved parking lots, roofs, driveways, etc.	98	98	98	98
Streets and roads:				
Paved with curbs and storm sewers	98	98	98	98
Gravel	76	85	89	91
Dirt	72	82	87	89
Paved with open ditches	83	89	92	93
Western desert urban areas:				
Natural desert landscaping (pervious area only)	63	77	85	88
Artificial desert landscaping	96	96	96	96
Developing urban areas				
Newly graded area	77	86	91	94
	Average % impervious			
Commercial and business	85	89	92	94
Industrial districts	72	81	88	91
Residential districts				
1/8 acre or less	65	77	85	90
1/4 acre	38	61	75	83
1/3 acre	30	57	72	81
1/2 acre	25	54	70	80
1 acre	20	51	68	79
2 acres	12	46	65	77
Fallow		77	86	91
Grass (bunch grass, or poor stand of sod)		51	70	80
Coffee (no ground cover, no terraces)		48	68	79
Coffee (with ground cover and terraces)		22	52	68
Tropical kudzu		19	50	67
Sugarcane (trash burned; straight-row)		43	65	77
Sugarcane (trash mulch; straight-row)		45	66	77
Sugarcane (in holes; on contour)		24	53	69
Sugarcane (in furrows; on contour)		32	58	72

Source: U.S. Department of Agriculture, -SCS, 1986.

In addition to the rational coefficient or the curve number, one important parameter that must be supplied is the time of concentration in minutes (not required for the SCS-Design Storm Method). The time of concentration could be calculated by using the miscellaneous calculator, which uses three different formulas. They are the Kirpich, the Curve Number (CN), and the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA).

The Kirpich formula is given in English units by the following equation:

$$T_c = .0078 \times \frac{L^{0.77}}{S^{0.385}}$$

And in Metric units by:

$$T_c = .0195 \times \frac{L^{0.77}}{S^{0.385}}$$

Where

- T_c is the time of concentration in minutes
- L is the length of travel in ft (English units), or m (Metric units).
- S is the slope in ft/ft (English units), or m/m (Metric units).

The Curve Number formula is given in English units by the following equation:

$$T_c = 100 \times \frac{L^{0.8} (S' + 1.00)^{0.7}}{1140.00 \times S^{0.5}}$$

And in Metric units by:

$$T_c = 100 \times \frac{L^{0.8} (S' + 25.4)^{0.7}}{4241.31 \times S^{0.5}}$$

Where

$$S' = K \times \left(\frac{1000}{CN} - 10 \right)$$

- T_c is the time of concentration in minutes
- L is the length of travel in ft (English units), or m (Metric units).
- S' is the soil storage capacity in inches (English units), or mm (Metric units)
- S is the slope in percentage.
- K is a conversion factor, $K=1.0$ for English units, $K=25.4$ for Metric units.
- CN is the soil curve number as previously defined.

The FAA formula is given in English units by the following equation:

$$T_c = 1.80 \times \frac{(1.1 - C)L^{0.5}}{S^{0.333}}$$

And in Metric units by:

$$T_c = 3.26 \times \frac{(1.1 - C)L^{0.5}}{S^{0.333}}$$

Where

T_c is the time of concentration in minutes

L is the length of travel in ft (English units), or m (Metric units).

S is the slope in percentage.

C is the soil runoff coefficient as previously defined.

If the SCS-flood hydrograph method is chosen, a variable known as the SCS peaking factor must be entered. This factor describes the length of the recession time T_r in relation with the peaking time T_p .

Figure 1: Dimensionless Triangular SCS Unit Hydrograph

The volume of the triangular unit hydrograph (Q_p) is calculated by finding the area under the triangle, which is also equal to the volume generated by a storm of 1-inch depth (i), of 1 hour duration (T), falling over an area (A) of 1 square mile (640 acres).

$$Q_p = \frac{q_p T_p}{2} + \frac{q_p T_r}{2} = \frac{q_p}{2} (T_p + T_r)$$

$$Q_p = i \times A \times T$$

Or by

Where q_p the peak flow is

$$q_p = \frac{2Q_p}{(T_p + T_r)} = \frac{2Q_p}{T_p \left(1 + \frac{T_r}{T_p}\right)} = \frac{K_p Q_p}{T_p}$$

and K_p the peak attenuation factor is

$$K_p = \frac{2}{\left(1 + \frac{T_r}{T_p}\right)}$$

Replacing Q_p by the product of the rainfall depth, the area, the time, and inserting the appropriate conversion factor for the flow q_p to be in cubic feet per second (ft^3/s), we then have:

$$q_p = 645.33 K_p \frac{(AQ_p)}{T_p}$$

If $T_r = 1.667 T_p$ then $K_p = 0.75$ and q_p reduces to

$$q_p = 484 \frac{(AQ_p)}{T_p}$$

Where T_p the time to peak is defined by:

$$T_p = \left(\frac{0.02 / 0.15}{2} \right) T_c + 0.6 T_c$$

The factor 484 is the typical SCS peaking factor. Other factors could be calculated for different hydrographs receding limb.

Table 3: Triangular Shaped Hydrograph Peak Attenuation Factor

Description	T _r	K _p	SCS (English units)	SCS (Metric units)
	24.8133 T _p	0.07748	50	0.02146
Rural very flat	11.9066 T _p	0.15496	100	0.04292
	5.4533 T _p	0.30992	200	0.08585
Rural slight slope	4.0416 T _p	0.39669	256	0.10988
	3.3022 T _p	0.46488	300	0.12878
Rural rolling hills	2.9959 T _p	0.50052	323	0.13864
	2.6876 T _p	0.54236	350	0.15023
Mixed urban/rural	2.2267 T _p	0.61983	400	0.17170
	1.8682 T _p	0.69731	450	0.19315
Typical SCS	1.6667 T _p	0.75000	484	0.20775
	1.5813 T _p	0.77479	500	0.21462
Urban steep slopes	1.3467 T _p	0.85227	550	0.23608
	1.1511 T _p	0.92975	600	0.25754
Rational	1.0000 T _p	1.00000	645.33	0.27777

Looking at the table, one noticed the SCS peaking factor in Metric units is not very easy to remember. Considering this, HYDFDR will only allow the SCS peaking factor in English units. For Metric analysis, the program will internally do the conversion.

5.0 EXFILTRATION TRENCH

In this section, the parameters describing an exfiltration trench are entered. Relevant to the analysis are the trench top and bottom width, the length, the critical elevation, the pipe shape, size, invert elevation and length, the soil infiltration rate, the design water table level and variation with time, and lastly a safety factor. Two analysis approaches are being promoted first by the South Florida Water Management District (SFWMD), and second by the Florida Department of Transportation District Six (FDOT-6).

As per the SFWMD, the exfiltration rate for a trench could be evaluated by the following formula:

$$EXF = 2KD_U \left(H_2 - \frac{1}{2} D_U \right) + 2KD_S H_2 + KH_2 W$$

Where

EXF is the trench exfiltration rate in m³/s (Metric units), or in ft³/s (English units)

K is the hydraulic conductivity in m³/s/m²/m of head, or ft³/s/ft²/ft of head

D_U is the unsaturated trench depth in m or ft

H₂ is the maximum hydraulic head acting on the water table surface, in m, or ft

D_S is the saturated trench depth in m, or ft

W is the trench bottom width in m, or ft

These variables are illustrated below.

Figure 2: Trench Parameters as per SFWMD

The FDOT-6 formula is very similar to the SFWMD formula except the exfiltration through the trench bottom is not considered, and the hydraulic conductivity instead of being averaged over the entire trench depth, is divided into three values. The hydraulic conductivity test calculates the soil infiltration at the 10 feet (3 meters), 15 feet (4 meters), and the 20 feet depth (6 meters).

The FDOT-6 formula is given by

$$EXF = 2K_{10}D_U \left(\frac{D_U}{2} + d_s \right) + 2K_{15}d_2D_U + 2K_{20}d_3D_U$$

Where

- EXF is the trench exfiltration rate in m^3/s (Metric units), or in ft^3/s (English units)
- K_{10} is the hydraulic conductivity in $m^3/s/m^2/m$ of head, or $ft^3/s/ft^2/ft$ of head at 10 feet
- K_{15} is the hydraulic conductivity in $m^3/s/m^2/m$ of head, or $ft^3/s/ft^2/ft$ of head at 15 feet
- K_{20} is the hydraulic conductivity in $m^3/s/m^2/m$ of head, or $ft^3/s/ft^2/ft$ of head at 20 feet
- D_U is the unsaturated trench depth in m or ft
- H_2 is the maximum hydraulic head acting on the water table surface, in m, or ft
- d_s is the saturated trench depth in m, or ft
- d_2 is the saturated trench depth in m, or ft at 15 feet depth
- d_3 is the saturated trench depth in m, or ft at 20 feet depth

These variables are illustrated in figure 3

Figure 3: Trench Parameters as per FDOT-6

These two equations could be combined into a series type formula to account for varying ground water level and different trench depth.

$$EXF = 2K_{10}d_{U1}\left(H_1 + \frac{1}{2}d_{U1}\right) + 2K_{15}d_{U2}\left(H_1 + d_{U1} + \frac{1}{2}d_{U2}\right) + 2K_{20}d_{U3}\left(H_1 + d_{U1} + d_{U2} + \frac{1}{2}d_{U3}\right) +$$

$$2K_{10}d_{S1}\left(H_1 + d_{U1}\right) + 2K_{15}d_{S2}\left(H_1 + d_{U1} + d_{U2}\right) + 2K_{20}d_{S3}\left(H_1 + d_{U1} + d_{U2} + d_{U3}\right) +$$

$$(K_{10}, K_{15}, K_{20})H_2W$$

Where the average pressure head H_1 is given by:

$$H_1 = H_2 - D_U$$

In addition to calculating the trench exfiltration capacity, HYDFDR also evaluates the trench total storage volume. This volume is based on the trench cross section and length, and on the conduit shape and length.

6.0 CONTROL STRUCTURE

HYDFDR has the capabilities of modelling four different type of weirs: rectangular, triangular, circular, or simply a rating curve that could represent a pump or a drainage well. This program also accounts for the effect of adverse tail water condition.

The rectangular weir formula as derived from the Bernoulli equation is given by:

$$Q = C_d \times \frac{2}{3} \times \sqrt{2G} \times L \times H_1^{3/2}$$

for the unsubmerged condition. And by the following for the submerged condition

$$Q = C_o \times \sqrt{2G} \times (L \times H_2) \times (H_1 - 0.5H_2)^{1/2}$$

Where

- Q is the weir capacity in m³/s (Metric units), or ft³/s (English units)
- C_d is the weir coefficient
- C_o is the orifice coefficient
- G is the acceleration due to gravity (9.81 m/s²), (32.2 ft/s²)
- L is the weir length in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)
- H_1 is the pressure head in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)
- H_2 is the height of the slot in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)

Typical value for C_o and C_d is 0.57

Similarly, for the unsubmerged triangular weir we have:

$$Q = C_d \times \frac{8}{15} \times \sqrt{2G} \times \tan\left(\frac{\Phi}{2}\right) \times H_1^{5/2}$$

And for the case of submerged triangular slot:

$$Q = C_o \times \sqrt{2G} \times \left(\frac{L \times H_2}{2}\right) \times \left(H_1 - \frac{2}{3}H_2\right)^{1/2}$$

Where

- Q is the weir capacity in m³/s (Metric units), or ft³/s (English units)
- C_d is the weir coefficient
- C_o is the orifice coefficient
- G is the acceleration due to gravity (9.81 m/s²), (32.2 ft/s²)
- Φ is the triangular weir central angle in degrees
- L is the triangular weir top width in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)
- H_1 is the pressure head in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)
- H_2 is the height of the slot in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)

Typical value for C_o and C_d is 0.57

For the unsubmerged circular weir, the following formula applies:

$$Q = C_d \times 2\sqrt{2G} \times \left[\frac{2^{9/2}}{15} R^{5/2} - (2R - H_1)^{3/2} \times \left(\frac{8}{15} R + \frac{2}{5} H_1 \right) \right]$$

and for the case of a submerged orifice the flow formula is:

$$Q = C_o \times \sqrt{2G} \times \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \times (H_1 - 0.5D)^{1/2}$$

Where

- Q is the weir capacity in m^3/s (Metric units), or ft^3/s (English units)
- C_d is the weir coefficient
- C_o is the orifice coefficient
- G is the acceleration due to gravity ($9.81 m/s^2$), ($32.2 ft/s^2$)
- D is the orifice diameter in mm (Metric units), or inches (English units)
- R is the orifice radius in mm (Metric units), or inches (English units)
- H_1 is the pressure head in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)

Typical value for C_o and C_d is 0.57

7.0 STORAGE BY AREAS

Often, a designer is asked to find how high the runoff from a storm event will pond over an inlet. This program allows the input of stage areas that will be translated into a stage volume. The formula used is based on the volume of a trunk of a pyramid. It is given by:

$$V = \frac{H}{3} (A_1 + A_2 + \sqrt{A_1 A_2})$$

Where

- V is the volume in Ha-m (Metric units), or in Ac-ft (English units)
- H is the head difference between 2 points, expressed in m or in ft
- A_1 is the area at a point 1 in Ha (Metric units), or in Ac (English units)
- A_2 is the area at a point 2 in Ha (Metric units), or in Ac (English units)

8.0 STORAGE BY VOLUME

Aside from supplying the potential storage by areas, HYDFDR also allows the user to input other storage sources by volume. These could be for example: underground chambers, sloping pipes, or reservoirs. For the case of sloping pipes, a very useful program is supplied in the miscellaneous calculator section. In this window, the user will enter the pipe shape and size, the upstream and

downstream invert, and finally the pipe length. The program then calculates the pipe volume using the prismoid equation defined by:

$$V = \frac{L}{6}(A_1 + A_2 + 4A_M)$$

Where

- V is the volume in Ha-m (Metric units), or Ac-ft (English units)
- L is the pipe length between 2 points, expressed in m or ft
- A_1 is the area at a point 1 in hectares (Metric units), or acres (English units)
- A_2 is the area at a point 2 in hectares (Metric units), or acres (English units)
- A_M is the mid-area between 1 and 2 in hectares, or acres

9.0 FLOOD ROUTING

The first task of HYDFDR is to create an overall stage-storage and stage-discharge curve for the site data being analyzed. The program will combine all stage-storage data supplied by the user into one single curve. For the case of a variable ground water table over time, additional total stage-storage curves are created to account for this variation. For the case of the stage-discharge, the program similarly to the case of the stage-storage, combines all the stage-discharge data into one overall stage-discharge curve. However, if the condition of variable tail water elevation exists, HYDFDR creates additional curves over the entire duration period being considered. Once these two curves or families of curves are created, the program proceeds to the creation of the site hydrograph, depending on the method selected.

9.1 The Rational-Critical Storm

This method is widely used for sizing detention facilities. The program creates a family of hydrographs based on the rational coefficient, the areas, the time of concentration and for different durations until a time limit set by the user. For each intensity value on the hydrograph, the runoff flow is calculated using the Rational formula.

$$Q = ciA$$

Where

- Q is the runoff flow in m^3/s (Metric units), or ft^3/s (English units)
- c is the rational coefficient as defined in table 1
- i is the intensity in mm/hr (Metric units), or $inch/hr$ (English units)
- A is the area in hectares (Metric units), or acres (English units)

A flood routing analysis is performed for each inflow hydrograph until the most critical is found. Theoretically, it is the hydrograph that produces the most runoff volume. However, this is not always the case. Typically, most designers will size a detention facility by considering only the runoff volume. This approach is only an approximation. The flood routing if performed, will show more often a different critical duration. Figure 4 illustrates the rational critical duration.

TYPICAL IDF CURVE

Figure 4: Critical Duration Rational Hydrograph.

9.2 The FDOT-Modified Rational

This method used the Rational formula, a total rainfall depth, and a given unit hydrograph to calculate the instantaneous flow at any given time. The FDOT has created many different hydrograph shapes for various duration. The idea is to perform a flood routing for each hydrograph until the most critical (higher stage, bigger volume) is found.

FDOT-1

Figure 5: Typical 1 hour Duration FDOT Unit Hydrograph.

9.3 The SCS-Santa Barbara

The Santa Barbara method is well adapted to urban hydrology. It was developed by James M. Stubchaer. This method is quite simple and does not overestimate the peak runoff of the hydrograph. The first step is to find the excess runoff based on the curve number CN or available soil storage for each ordinate of the user supplied unit hydrograph. The excess runoff is calculated using the following equation.

$$R_{(t)} = \frac{(P_{(t)} - 0.2S')^2}{(P_{(t)} + 0.8S')}$$

Where

- $R_{(t)}$ is the excess runoff depth at time T, in millimeters, or inches
 $P_{(t)}$ is the cumulative rainfall depth at time T, in millimeters, or inches
 S' is the soil storage capacity as previously defined

And the constant 0.2 is the initial abstraction.

Once the cumulative runoff depth is calculated, the instantaneous hydrograph is computed for each time period.

$$I_{(t)} = \left(\frac{R_{(t)} - R_{(t-\Delta t)}}{\Delta t} \right) \times A$$

Where

- $I_{(t)}$ is the instantaneous hydrograph flow in m³/s, or in ft³/s
 $R_{(t)}$ is the excess runoff depth at time T, in millimeters, or inches
 Δt is the incremental time period (routing interval)
 A is the total basin area in hectares (Metric units), or in acres (English units)

The final hydrograph or watershed hydrograph is then obtained by routing the instantaneous hydrograph by a routing constant or lag factor K_r . This variable is not to be confused with the SCS peak attenuation factor K_p .

$$Q_{(t+\Delta t)} = Q_{(t)} + K_r \times (I_{(t)} + I_{(t+\Delta t)} - 2Q_{(t)})$$

Where

$$K_r = \left(\frac{\Delta t}{2T_c + \Delta t} \right)$$

Once the flow hydrograph is created, the program proceeds to the flood routing analysis.

9.4 The SCS-Design Storm

This method is used when the basin being analyzed is small as compared to the regional basin. The regional basin hydrograph is created by empirical analysis of rainfall records. In applying this

method to a small basin, the location of the peak stage and outflow is driven by the peak location in time of the regional hydrograph. Some design hydrograph will have one peak, while others will have two or more peaks. Once a design storm is selected, the first step is to calculate the excess runoff based on the curve number at different time step along the storm duration.

$$R_{(t)} = \frac{(P_{(t)} - 0.2S')^2}{(P_{(t)} + 0.8S')}$$

Where the variables were previously defined.

Once the cumulative runoff depth is calculated, the instantaneous hydrograph is computed for each time period.

$$I_{(t)} = \left(\frac{R_{(t)} - R_{(t-\Delta t)}}{\Delta t} \right) \times A$$

As before, the variables in this equation were previously defined.

This procedure is applied for any type of design storm for specific duration and rainfall depth. Figure 6 shows a typical FDOT hydrograph with a 10-day duration.

Figure 6: Typical 10 days Duration FDOT Unit Hydrograph.

9.5 The SCS-Flood Hydrograph

The SCS flood hydrograph method is a very tedious procedure. The first step is to compute a unit hydrograph for the basin being analyzed. This unit hydrograph could be the triangular, or curvilinear shape with the recession limb as defined by K_p the peak attenuation factor. HYDFDR

uses the Gamma distribution function to calculate the ordinates of the hydrograph. This method was first presented by Aaron and White in 1982. The unit hydrograph is calculated by:

$$q(f) = q_{(t)} = q_p f^a e^{a(1-f)}$$

Where a is defined by:

$$a = 0.045 + 0.5f_a + 5.6f_a^2 + 0.3f_a^3$$

And f_a by:

$$f_a = \frac{q_p t_p}{A}$$

Where

q_p is the peak flow occurring at time t_p , (time to peak) previously described

A is the basin area in hectares (Metric units), or in acres (English units)

f is a parameter of t_p

The comparison between the triangular, SCS, and Gamma distribution hydrograph is shown in figure 7.

UNIT HYDROGRAPH K=484

Figure 7: Comparison between different unit hydrograph shapes.

Once the unit hydrograph is created, the next step is to calculate the excess runoff based on the curve number. The excess runoff equation is used.

$$R_{(t)} = \frac{(P_{(t)} - 0.2S')^2}{(P_{(t)} + 0.8S')}$$

Once the cumulative runoff depth is calculated, the instantaneous hydrograph is computed for each time period.

$$I_{(t)} = \left(\frac{R_{(t)} - R_{(t-\Delta t)}}{\Delta t} \right)$$

Note the watershed area is not included here but rather in the Gamma function.

Finally, the watershed hydrograph is found by multiplying the unit hydrograph defined by $q_{(t)}$ by the instantaneous hydrograph $I_{(t)}$ in the following manner.

At time t_1

$$Q_1 = q_1 I_1$$

At time t_2

$$Q_2 = q_1 I_1 + q_2 I_2$$

At time t_3

$$Q_3 = q_1 I_1 + q_2 I_2 + q_3 I_3$$

At time t_4

$$Q_4 = q_1 I_1 + q_2 I_2 + q_3 I_3 + q_4 I_4$$

And so on until the final storm duration is reached.

Having created the watershed hydrograph by one of the five methods described, HYDFDR proceeds to perform a flood routing analysis by the storage indication method based on the conservation of mass or continuity equation. The inflow (I), outflow (O) and storage (S) are related by

$$I - O = \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta T}$$

This equation could be rearranged and rewritten as

$$\frac{1}{2}(I_1 + I_2)\Delta T + \left(S_1 - \frac{1}{2}O_1\Delta T\right) = \left(S_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2\Delta T\right)$$

At time t_1 , the variables I_1 , O_1 , S_1 , and the initial stage EL_1 are known, and at time t_2 the variable I_2 is also known. Replacing all the variables into the equation, the right side representing $(S_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2\Delta t)$ is calculated. In addition to a stage-storage or a stage-discharge curve, it is necessary to have a relationship between O_2 and $(S_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2\Delta t)$ as another plotted curve. From the $(S_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2\Delta t)$ curve, the value of O_2 is determined, and from the stage-discharge curve, the stage EL_2 at time t_2 is evaluate. From the stage EL_2 , and using the stage-storage curve, the value of S_2 is determined. The variables O_2 , S_2 , EL_2 become the initial condition for the next time step t_3 . The process is repeated by Δt increment until some set time constraint is reached. In performing this computation, the smaller the time increment, the more accurate the routing result will be.

10.0 MAIN MENU

The first window displays 16 icons

“NEW”

This icon will clear a project from memory.

“OPEN”

This icon will open a project file (filename.fdr).

“SAVE”

This icon will save a project file (filename.fdr).

“UNIT”

This icon will set up the project unit, either in “Metric” or “English”.

“PROJECT”

This icon will open the project data window.

“ANALYSIS METHOD”

This icon will open the method of analysis window.

“BASIN DATA”

This icon will open the watershed basin area window.

“TRENCH DATA”

This icon will open the exfiltration trench window consisting of 4 different tabs.

“WEIR DATA”

This icon will open the control structure window with 5 different types of weirs.

“STAGE AREA”

This icon will open the stage-area window for additional storage.

“STAGE STORAGE”

This icon will open the stage-storage window.

“ROUTING”

This icon will open the routing data window.

“STORM LIBRARY”

This icon will open either the SCS or the IDF storm library depending on the method.

“PIPE LIBRARY”

This icon will open the pipe library with 4 different shapes.

“CALCULATOR”

This icon will open the calculator window.

“HELP ABOUT”

This icon will open the “About” window.

10.1 Design Unit

By clicking on either option, the project unit will be changed, and all the data transformed accordingly.

10.2 Project Data

The image shows a software dialog box titled "Project". It contains a section labeled "Project Informations" with five input fields, each with a label on the left and a text box on the right. The fields are: "Project Number" with the value "SAMPLE PROBLEM", "Project Location" with "MIAMI DADE COUNTY", "Company Name" with "FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION", "Client Name" with "CITY OF MIAMI", and "Designer Name" with "F.M.". At the bottom right of the dialog box are two buttons: "Clear" and "OK".

Field Label	Value
Project Number	SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location	MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name	FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name	CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name	F.M.

The information entered here will be displayed on the printout.

10.3 Analysis Method

This window allows the user to specify which method to use for the analysis of the exfiltration trench.

10.4 Watershed Data

The screenshot shows a software window titled "Watershed" with a "Basin Data" section. The window contains several input fields and buttons. The "Basin Description" field is filled with "SAMPLE PROBLEM SFWMD-DERM, SITE ABOVE FLOOD PLAIN". There are three rows of data for different areas, each with an area value, a unit "Ac", a Curve Number (CN) value, and a land use type. The "Total" row shows a total area of 0.00 Ac and a CN Avg. of 0.00. The "Time of concentration" is set to 10.00 Minutes, and the "Peak Factor" is set to 256.00. At the bottom of the window are four buttons: "Solve", "Report", "Clear", and "OK".

Basin Data					
Basin Description		SAMPLE PROBLEM SFWMD-DERM, SITE ABOVE FLOOD PLAIN			
Area 1 =	0.69	Ac	CN 1 =	98.00	BUILDING
Area 2 =	0.79	Ac	CN 2 =	98.00	PARKING
Area 3 =	1.52	Ac	CN 3 =	66.89	GREEN SPACE
Total	0.00	Ac	CN Avg.	0.00	
Time of concentration	10.00	Minutes	Peak Factor =	256.00	

Solve Report Clear OK

The Project basin areas are entered in this window. Depending on the method used, the land use coefficient could be either the Rational Coefficient or the Curve Number. For the case of the SCS-Flood Hydrograph, the peaking factor must be entered.

A total of four command buttons are available.

- "SOLVE"** Performs the calculation, and displays the total area.
- "REPORT"** Sends the displayed output to the printer.
- "CLEAR"** Resets the current data.
- "OK"** Close the window.

10.5 Trench Data

10.5.1 Trench Data

The screenshot shows a software window titled "TRENCH DATA" with four tabs: "Trench Data", "Conduit Data", "Soil Data", and "Water Table". The "Trench Data" tab is active and contains the following input fields:

Trench Data		Conduit Data		Soil Data		Water Table	
Bottom El.	-4.50	ft	Bottom Width	3.00	ft		
Top El.	4.00	ft	Top Width	3.00	ft		
Min. Inlet El.	5.50	ft					
Trench Length	365.00	ft					
Safety Factor	2.00						

Below the input fields is a "Sketch" area showing a cross-section of a trench with a circular conduit inside. A horizontal line indicates the ground surface, and another horizontal line indicates the trench bottom. The trench walls are shown as vertical lines, and the conduit is a circle centered within the trench.

To the right of the sketch is the "Trench Capacity" section, which displays calculated values:

Gross Trench Vol.	9307.5000	ft ³
Effective Trench Vol.	871.0388	ft ³
Total Trench Vol.	1318.9612	ft ³
Total Exf. Rate	4.2158	ft ³ /s

At the bottom of the window are four buttons: "Solve", "Report", "Clear", and "OK".

The user enters the trench section defined by the bottom width and elevation, the top width and elevation, the critical inlet elevation, the trench length, and a safety factor that will be applied to the total exfiltration rate.

A total of four commands are provided. These commands work also for the other input tab.

- "SOLVE"** Performs the calculation, and fills in the "Trench Capacity" data.
- "REPORT"** Sends the displayed output values and sketches to the printer.
- "CLEAR"** Resets the current data.
- "OK"** Close the window.

10.5.2 Conduit Data

Field	Value	Unit
Shape	CIRCULAR PIPE	
Denomination	15 inch	
Span	15.00	in
Rise	15.00	in
Invert El.	2.00	ft
Pipe Length	365.00	ft
Area	1.2272	ft ²
Perimeter	3.9270	ft
Submerged Pipe Vol.	0.0000	ft ³
Unsubmerged Pipe Vol.	447.9224	ft ³

The user chooses a pipe size based on four different pipe shapes. The pipe invert elevation and length are also specified. The same commands available for the trench data section are also enabled in the conduit data section, but with slightly different results.

- “SOLVE”** Performs the calculation, and fills in the “Pipe Properties” data.
- “REPORT”** Sends the displayed output values and sketches to the printer.
- “CLEAR”** Resets the current data.
- “OK”** Close the window.

10.5.3 Soil Data

The screenshot shows a software dialog box titled "TRENCH DATA" with four tabs: "Trench Data", "Conduit Data", "Soil Data" (selected), and "Water Table".

Design Water Table El. ft

Exfiltration Rate Test Result

K10 Hyd. Cond.	<input type="text" value="3.50 E-04"/>	ft ³ /s /ft ² /ft	K10 Test El.	<input type="text" value="2.00"/>	ft
K15 Hyd. Cond.	<input type="text" value="3.50 E-04"/>	ft ³ /s /ft ² /ft	K15 Test El.	<input type="text" value="-2.00"/>	ft
K20 Hyd. Cond.	<input type="text" value="3.50 E-04"/>	ft ³ /s /ft ² /ft	K20 Test El.	<input type="text" value="-5.00"/>	ft

Allowed Exfiltration Plane

- Exfiltration Thru Trench Right Side**
- Exfiltration Thru Trench Left Side**
- Exfiltration Thru Trench Bottom**

Buttons:

The user specifies the design water table elevation, the exfiltration rates at the K10, K15, and K20 level. Furthermore, the user has the option to disable or enable the trench exfiltration on the right, the left, or the bottom.

10.5.4 Water Table

In this window, different water table elevation versus time can be specified.

10.6 Weir Data

10.6.1 Rectangular Weir

WEIR DATA
X

Rectangular
Triangular
Circular
User Defined
Tail Water

Weir Description	CONTROL STRUCTURE (RECTANGULAR TRIAL)		
-------------------------	---------------------------------------	--	--

Max. Stage El. =	5.00	ft
Inv. El. =	4.00	ft
Weir Length =	5.000	ft
Weir Height =	1.000	ft
Incremental dh. =	0.250	ft

$$Q = C_d \frac{2}{3} L \sqrt{2g} H^{3/2}$$

No. of Weir =	1
Weir Coefficient =	0.58
Orifice Coefficient =	0.62

Point	Stage	Flow
1	4.000	0.000
2	4.250	1.939
3	4.500	5.485
4	4.750	10.077

Solve
Graph
Report
Clear
OK

For the rectangular weir, the user specifies the maximum ponding stage that can occur within a detention area, the weir invert elevation, the length, and for the case of a rectangular slot the weir height. More than one weir can be entered. The check box at the top of the page will enable or disable the rectangular weir. The incremental height is for analysis purpose and decides how accurate the flow curve needs to be. The user has also the option of entering different weir or orifice coefficient. A total of five commands are provided.

- “**SOLVE**” Performs the calculation, draws the graph, and fills the flow table.
- “**GRAPH**” Performs the calculation, and draws the graph.
- “**REPORT**” Sends the displayed output values and sketches to the printer.
- “**CLEAR**” Resets the current data.
- “**OK**” Close the window.

10.6.2 Triangular Weir

WEIR DATA
✕

Rectangular
Triangular
Circular
User Defined
Tail Water

Weir Description CONTROL STRUCTURE (TRIANGULAR TRIAL)

Max. Stage El. =	5.00	ft
Inv. El. =	4.00	ft
Weir Angle =	25.000	Deg.
Weir Height =	1.000	ft
Incremental dh. =	0.25	ft

$$Q = C_d \frac{8}{15} \tan\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \sqrt{2g} H^{5/2}$$

No. of Weir =	1
Weir Coefficient =	0.58
Orifice Coefficient =	0.62

Point	Stage	Flow
1	4.000	0.000
2	4.250	0.017
3	4.500	0.097
4	4.750	0.268

Solve
Graph
Report
Clear
OK

The data required are similar to the rectangular weir, except for the triangular weir central angle.

10.6.3 Circular Weir

WEIR DATA X

Rectangular
Triangular
Circular
User Defined
Tail Water

Weir Description CONTROL STRUCTURE (BLEEDER ORIFICE TRIAL)

Max. Stage El. = 5.00 ft

$Q = C_d A \sqrt{2g} H^{3/2}$

Inv. El. = 4.00 ft

Span = 4.000 inch

No. of Weir = 1

Rise = 4.000 inch

Weir Coefficient = 0.58

Incremental dh. = 0.13 ft

Orifice Coefficient = 0.62

Point	Stage	Flow
1	4.000	0.000
2	4.130	0.039
3	4.260	0.124
4	4.390	0.186
5	4.520	0.248
6	4.650	0.302
7	4.780	0.340
8	4.910	0.374

Solve
Graph
Report
Clear
OK

The circular weir (orifice) data are similar to the rectangular, or triangular weir. The orifice diameter is entered as span and rise. The rise is always equal to the span.

10.6.4 User Defined

The user defined weir could be a pump, a drainage well, or an overflow structure with already defined values. The user enters the data into the table. Negative values are allowed. Data lines can be inserted, deleted, copied or pasted.

10.6.5 Tail Water

The image shows a software window titled "WEIR DATA" with a "Tail Water" tab selected. The window contains a table titled "TAIL WATER ELEVATIONS VARIATIONS VERSUS TIME" with the following data:

	Duration	Stage
1	0.000	2.000
2	24.000	2.500
3	48.000	3.500
4	60.000	5.000
5	72.000	2.000

Buttons for "Insert", "Delete", "Clear", "Copy", and "Paste" are located to the right of the table. At the bottom of the window are buttons for "Solve", "Graph", "Report", "Clear", and "OK".

In this window, different tail water elevation versus time can be specified. This option is useful to evaluate the effect of the receiving water body toward the control structure.

10.7 Stage Storage by Area Data

When additional storage is available, the stage storage by area option can be used. The data points are entered in the table, and can be manipulated, copied or pasted in other record.

A total of eight command buttons are available.

- "PREV"** Displays the previous data.
- "NEXT"** Displays the next data.
- "SOLVE"** Performs the analysis, draws the graph, and fills in the storage values.
- "ADD"** Adds a data to the last record.
- "INSERT"** Inserts a data at the current record position.
- "DELETE"** Deletes the current data.
- "REPORT"** Sends the displayed output values to the printer.
- "OK"** Close the window.

There is no limit on the amount of stage area records a data file can have.

10.8 Stage Storage by Volume Data

When additional storage is available, the stage storage by volume option can be used. The data points are entered in the table, and can be manipulated, copied or pasted in other record.

A total of eight command buttons are available.

- "PREV"** Displays the previous data.
- "NEXT"** Displays the next data.
- "GRAPH"** Draws the graph.
- "ADD"** Adds a data to the last record.
- "INSERT"** Inserts a data at the current record position.
- "DELETE"** Deletes the current data.
- "REPORT"** Sends the displayed output values to the printer.
- "OK"** Close the window.

There is no limit on the amount of stage area record a data file can have.

10.9 Routing Analysis Data

10.9.1 Setting

The screenshot shows the 'SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD' software window. At the top, there are fields for 'Analysis No.' (59) and 'Description' (Miami-Dade 25 Year 6 Hour Storm). Below this are tabs for 'Setting', 'Ground Water', 'Tail Water', 'Graph', and 'Table', with 'Setting' currently selected. The 'Input Values' section on the left contains several fields: 'Unit Hydrograph Name' (SCSII-6), 'Storm Duration' (6.00 Hours), 'Maximum Rainfall Depth' (8.40 inches), 'Maximum Routing Time' (6.00 Hours), 'Flood Routing Time Step' (0.25 Minutes), and 'Print Display Time Step' (1.00 Minutes). The 'Analysis Status' section on the right lists eight items, each with a green checkmark: 'Basin Area', 'Trench Data', 'Weir Data', 'Stage-Area', 'Stage-Volume', 'Total Storage', 'Total Outflow', 'Inflow Hydrograph', and 'Flood Routing'. At the bottom of the window are buttons for '< Prev', 'Next >', 'Solve', 'Add', 'Insert', 'Delete', 'Report', and 'OK'.

Depending on the analysis method, this window will be altered accordingly. Displayed is the Rational-Critical Storm. The user selects the intensity duration frequency curve (IDF) from a set of predefined curves. Required data are: the time to stop the analysis, the time increment for both the runoff envelope and the routing analysis. Required also is the printing time increment to set the graphs and the tables. On the right side of this window are listed critical steps in the analysis procedures. If the analysis is without errors, a green shaded box will appear next to the step being performed. Otherwise, the appropriate box will be shaded in red.

A total of eight options similar to the stage storage by area window are provided. The amount of analysis event is virtually limitless.

10.9.2 Graph

A total of eight graphs can be plotted and printed. They are the “stage-storage”, “stage-discharge”, “runoff-envelope”, “mass curve”, “stage-duration”, “inflow-duration”, “outflow duration”, and the “inflow-outflow-duration”. By clicking on the command button labeled “report”, a plotted copy of the displayed graph can be obtained.

10.9.3 Table

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD

Analysis No. 59 Description Miami-Dade 25 Year 6 Hour Storm

Setting Ground Water Tail Water Graph Table

STAGE - DURATION	
TIME	STAGE
(Min.)	(ft)
0.000	2.700
1.000	2.700
2.000	2.700
3.000	2.700
4.000	2.700
5.000	2.700
6.000	2.700
7.000	2.700
8.000	2.700
9.000	2.700
10.000	2.700
11.000	2.700
12.000	2.700
13.000	2.700
14.000	2.700
15.000	2.700

Stage-Storage

Stage-Discharge

Mass Curve

Stage-Duration

Inflow-Duration

Outflow-Duration

Inflow-Outflow

Display Stage Variation Versus Storm Duration Table

< Prev Next > Solve Add Insert Delete Report OK

A total of eight tables can be printed. They are the “stage-storage”, “stage-discharge”, “runoff-envelope”, “mass curve”, “stage-duration”, “inflow-duration”, “outflow duration”, and the “inflow-outflow-duration”. By clicking on the command button labeled “report”, a printed copy of the displayed table can be obtained. One useful option is to highlight the table displayed, copy it, and paste it in another application.

10.10 Storm Library

10.10.1 SCS unit hydrograph

This window is to update and modified the unit hydrograph storm library. The number of unit hydrograph stored in a library is virtually limitless.

A total of eight command buttons are available.

- "PREV"** Displays the previous data.
- "NEXT"** Displays the next data.
- "GRAPH"** Draws the graph.
- "ADD"** Adds a data to the last record.
- "INSERT"** Inserts a data at the current record position.
- "DELETE"** Deletes the current data.
- "REPORT"** Sends the displayed output values to the printer.
- "OK"** Close the window.

10.11 Storm Library

IDF curves (2 type of equations)

10.11.1 Equation 1

IDF CURVE LIBRARY

IDF Curve No. Name

Equation 1 Equation 2

$$i = a + b[\ln(T_c)] + c[\ln(T_c)]^2 + d[\ln(T_c)]^3 \quad \text{inch/hr}$$

English Unit

a = b = c = d =

Metric Unit

a = b = c = d =

Graph

Point	Duration	Intensity
1	5.00	7.216
2	10.00	5.673
3	15.00	4.830
4	20.00	4.263
5	25.00	3.843
6	30.00	3.513
7	35.00	3.246
8	40.00	3.021
9	45.00	2.830

< Prev Next > Graph Add Insert Delete Report OK

This window allows the user to update the IDF curve library. Two options based on different equations are allowed. The data entered are dynamically converted to either the Metric or English unit. The eight commands available are similar to the unit hydrograph window.

10.11.2 Equation 2

IDF CURVE LIBRARY

IDF Curve No. 72 Name DADE50YEAR

Equation 1 Equation 2

$$i = \frac{a}{(b + T_c)^n} \text{ inch/hr}$$

English Unit

a = 465.853000 b = 47.724710 R = 1.000000

Metric Unit

a = 11832.666200 b = 47.724710 R = 1.000000

Point	Duration	Intensity
1	5.00	8.836
2	10.00	8.070
3	15.00	7.427
4	20.00	6.879
5	25.00	6.406
6	30.00	5.994
7	35.00	5.631
8	40.00	5.310
9	45.00	5.024

< Prev Next > Graph Add Insert Delete Report OK

10.12 Pipe Library

10.12.1 Circular

English Unit Pipe		Metric Unit Pipe	
Denomination	48 inch	Denomination	1200 mm
Span	48.00 inch	Span	1219.20 mm
Rise	48.00 inch	Rise	1219.20 mm
Rb	24.00 inch	Rb	609.60 mm
Rt	24.00 inch	Rt	609.60 mm
Rc	24.00 inch	Rc	609.60 mm

Pipe Properties	
Area	12.5664 ft ²
Perimeter	12.5664 ft
Hyd. Radius	1.0000 ft

Different circular pipe conduit can be created. The data entered are dynamically converted into either the English or the Metric unit.

10.12.2 Elliptical

English Unit Pipe			Metric Unit Pipe		
Denomination	12 x 18 inch		Denomination	305 x 460 mm	
Span	12.00	inch	Span	304.80	mm
Rise	18.00	inch	Rise	457.20	mm
Rb	5.00	inch	Rb	127.00	mm
Rt	5.00	inch	Rt	127.00	mm
Rc	13.50	inch	Rc	342.90	mm

Pipe Properties		
Area	1.1988	ft ²
Perimeter	4.0062	ft
Hyd. Radius	0.2992	ft

Different elliptical pipe conduit can be created. The data entered are dynamically converted into either the English or the Metric unit.

Depending on the corner radius or the top and bottom radius, a vertical or a horizontal ellipse can be created.

10.12.3 Arch

Pipe Library

Shape: Arch Pipe

English Unit Pipe			Metric Unit Pipe		
Denomination	17 x 13 inch		Denomination	450 x 340 mm	
Span	17.25	inch	Span	438.15	mm
Rise	13.00	inch	Rise	330.20	mm
Rb	25.63	inch	Rb	651.00	mm
Rt	8.63	inch	Rt	219.20	mm
Rc	3.50	inch	Rc	88.90	mm

Sketch

Pipe Properties

Area	1.2582	ft ²
Perimeter	4.0821	ft
Hyd. Radius	0.3082	ft

< Prev Next > Plot Add Insert Delete Report OK

Different arch pipe conduit can be created. The data entered are dynamically converted into either the English or the Metric unit. Because of the four segments procedure, an upside down arch section could be created.

10.12.4 Rectangular

English Unit Pipe		Metric Unit Pipe	
Denomination	36 x 36 inch	Denomination	900 x 900 mm
Span	36.00 inch	Span	914.40 mm
Rise	36.00 inch	Rise	914.40 mm
Rb	0.00 inch	Rb	0.00 mm
Rt	0.00 inch	Rt	0.00 mm
Rc	0.00 inch	Rc	0.00 mm

Pipe Properties	
Area	9.0000 ft ²
Perimeter	12.0000 ft
Hyd. Radius	0.7500 ft

Different rectangular pipe conduit can be created. The data entered are dynamically converted into either the English or the Metric unit.

10.13 Miscellaneous Calculator

10.13.1 Curve Fit

The screenshot shows the 'MISCELLANEOUS CALCULATOR' window with the 'Curve Fit' tab selected. The window is divided into three sections: 'Curve Fit', 'PIPE VOLUME', and 'TIME OF CONCENTRATION'. The 'Curve Fit' section contains an 'Input Values' table with 5 rows and 4 columns. To the right of the table are five buttons: 'Insert', 'Delete', 'Clear', 'Copy', and 'Paste'. Further right is the equation $i = \frac{a}{(b + T_c)^n}$ and three output fields for 'a = 35.82508', 'b = 0.99999', and 'n = 0.53331'. At the bottom right, there are 'Solve' and 'OK' buttons.

	Time	Intensity	Intensity
1	5.000	12.750	13.778
2	10.000	10.200	9.973
3	30.000	6.100	5.739
4	50.000	4.500	4.401
5	60.000	4.000	4.000

$i = \frac{a}{(b + T_c)^n}$

a = 35.82508
b = 0.99999
n = 0.53331

Solve OK

For the case of unknown IDF curve, the user has the capability of curve fitting an equation through some defined data points. By clicking on the command button “solve”, the curve fitting computation is performed and the right column of the input table displays the curve fitting values. The equation parameters are also displayed.

10.13.2 Pipe Volume

	Stage (ft)	Storage (Ac-ft)
1	2.250	0.0000
2	2.500	0.0002
3	3.750	0.0039
4	4.000	0.0041

Sloping pipe volume can be calculated by specifying the pipe shape, size, upstream and downstream invert, and the length. When calculating the volume, the data displayed in the table are also written in a temporary file. The results can be later pasted in the stage storage by volume window.

10.13.3 Time of Concentration

MISCELLANEOUS CALCULATOR

Curve Fit PIPE VOLUME TIME OF CONCENTRATION

Kirpich Curve Number FAA

Length = 250.00 ft

Slope = 0.00050 ft/ft

$$T_c = 0.0078 \times \frac{L^{0.77}}{S^{0.385}}$$

Time of Concentration is : 10.22 Minutes

Solve OK

Three different formulas are provided. By pressing the “solve” command button, the time of concentration is calculated.

10.14 Help About

This window displays the version, author, and copyright label. This program can be ordered free of charge as a package from the following contact:

Francis Mitchell, M.S., P.E.
f-mitchell@att.net
Phone: (305) 979-6387

Or by accessing the link below,

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/jf8vsmhhq013mdd/AACJfnUjpiiCieTCusBS0JxEa?dl=0>

10.15 Sample Printouts

WATERSHED DATA SAMPLE OUTPUT

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

Basin Area Report - SCS - Flood Hydrograph Method

Input Values

Area Ac	C	CN	Description
3.000	0.90	98.00	PAVED AREA
1.000	0.30	65.00	GRASS AREA
0.000	0.00	0.00	

Output Values

Basin Ac	C avg.	CN avg.	Description
4.000	0.75	89.75	SOUTH RIVER DRIVE

Time of concentration is 10 Minutes

Basin Peaking Factor is 256

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TRENCH DATA SAMPLE OUTPUT (sheet 1 of 3)

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
 Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
 Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
 Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
 Designer Name : F.M.

Exfiltration Trench Analysis Data

Input Values

Trench Bottom Elevation = -7.000 ft Trench Bottom Width = 3.000 ft
 Trench Top Elevation = 7.500 ft Trench Top Width = 5.590 ft
 Minimum Control Elevation = 8.000 ft
 Trench Total Length = 426.500 ft
 Trench Safety Factor = 2.000
 Conduit Shape is a CIRCULAR PIPE and 36 inch in Denomination
 Conduit Span = 36.000 in
 Conduit Rise = 36.000 in
 Conduit Invert Elevation = 2.700 ft
 Conduit Total Length = 426.500 ft
 Water Table Elevation = 2.700 ft

K10 Hyd. Conductivity	= 1.52 E-04 ft ³ /s /ft ² /ft	K10 Test Elevation	= -2.000 ft
K15 Hyd. Conductivity	= 3.48 E-04 ft ³ /s /ft ² /ft	K15 Test Elevation	= -7.000 ft
K20 Hyd. Conductivity	= 0.00 E+00 ft ³ /s /ft ² /ft	K20 Test Elevation	= -12.000 ft

Exfiltration Thru Trench Right Side Included.

Exfiltration Thru Trench Left Side Included.

Exfiltration Thru Trench Bottom not Accounted for.

Output Values

Unsubmerged Pipe Volume	= 3014.751	ft ³
Submerged Pipe Volume	= 0.000	ft ³
Gross Trench Volume	= 26561.354	ft ³
Effective Trench Volume	= 3775.742	ft ³
Total Net Trench Volume	= 6790.493	ft ³
Total Trench Exfiltration Rate	= 6.450	ft ³ /s

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(sheet 2 of 3)

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

Exfiltration Trench Analysis Data

Trench Sketch

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(sheet 3 of 3)

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - General Routing Data

Ground Water Table Elevations Variations

TIME (hours)	STAGE (ft)
0.000	2.7000
1.000	2.7000

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WEIR DATA SAMPLE OUTPUT (sheet 1 of 3)

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

Exfiltration Trench Analysis Data - Control Structure

Input Values - Rectangular Weir

Rectangular Weir Description : OVERFLOW STRUCTURE

Maximum Stage Elevation = 8.000 ft

Weir Invert Elevation = 7.500 ft

Weir Overall Length = 3.000 ft

Weir Total Height = 0.500 ft

Weir Incremental Unit Height = 0.100 ft

Weir Unsubmerged Coefficient = 0.58

Weir Submerged Coefficient = 0.62

Amount of Rectangular Weir = 1

Rectangular Weir is Enabled for the Exfiltration Trench Analysis

Output Values - Rating Curve

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(sheet 3 of 3)

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - General Routing Data

Tail Water Elevations Variations

TIME (hours)	STAGE (ft)
0.00	2.700
1.00	2.700

STAGE STORAGE BY AREA SAMPLE OUTPUT (sheet 1 of 2)

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

Exfiltration Trench Analysis Data - Stage-Area

Input Values - Stage Storage by Area

Stage-Area Number 1

Stage-Area Description : PAVED AREA (STORAGE ABOVE INLET)

Output Values - Rating Curve

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – ROUTING SUMMARY SHEET

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - General Routing Data

Description : 1 hour 2 year storm
Hydrograph name : FDOT-1
Rainfall depth : 2.62 inches
Rainfall duration : 1.00 Hour(s)
Time step interval: .25 Minutes
Maximum inflow volume is 0.520 Ac-ft
Maximum outflow volume is 0.335 Ac-ft
Minimum storage volume required is 0.186 Ac-ft
Maximum stage of 8.508 ft occurs at 0 Hours 45 Minutes
Maximum inflow of 13.934 ft³/s occurs at 0 Hours 42 Minutes
Maximum system outflow of 13.633 ft³/s occurs at 0 Hours 45 Minutes
Maximum exfiltration trench outflow is 7.140 ft³/s
At maximum exfiltration trench outflow, ground water elevation is 2.700 ft

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – TOTAL STAGE STORAGE CURVE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Total Site Stage Storage

Description : 1 hour 2 year storm
Hydrograph name : FDOT-1
Rainfall depth : 2.62 inches
Rainfall duration : 1.00 Hour(s)
At elevation 10.000 ft , the total site storage is 1.018 Ac-ft

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – TOTAL STAGE DISCHARGE CURVE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Total Site Stage Discharge

Description : 1 hour 2 year storm
Hydrograph Name : FDOT-1
Rainfall depth : 2.62 inches
Rainfall duration : 1.00 Hour(s)
At elevation 10.000 ft , the total site discharge is 20.361 ft³/s

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – MASS INFLOW-OUTFLOW CURVE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Mass Curve

Description : 1 hour 2 year storm
Hydrograph Name : FDOT-1
Rainfall depth : 2.62 inches
Rainfall duration : 1.00 Hour(s)
Maximum inflow volume is 0.520 Ac-ft
Maximum outflow volume is 0.335 Ac-ft
Minimum storage volume required is 0.186 Ac-ft

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – STAGE DURATION CURVE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Stage Duration

Description : 1 hour 2 year storm
Hydrograph Name : FDOT-1
Rainfall depth : 2.62 inches
Rainfall duration : 1.00 Hour(s)
Maximum stage of 8.508 ft occurs at 0 Hours 45 Minutes

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – INFLOW HYDROGRAPH CURVE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Inflow Duration

Description : 1 hour 2 year storm
Hydrograph Name : FDOT-1
Rainfall depth : 2.62 inches
Rainfall duration : 1.00 Hour(s)
Maximum inflow of 13.934 ft³/s occurs at 0 Hours 42 Minutes

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – OUTFLOW HYDROGRAPH CURVE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Outflow Duration

Description : 1 hour 2 year storm
Hydrograph Name : FDOT-1
Rainfall depth : 2.62 inches
Rainfall duration : 1.00 Hour(s)
Maximum outflow of 13.633 ft³/s occurs at 0 Hours 45 Minutes

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – INFLOW, OUTFLOW HYDROGRAPH

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Inflow-Outflow Duration

Description : 1 hour 2 year storm
Hydrograph name : FDOT-1
Rainfall depth : 2.62 inches
Rainfall duration : 1.00 Hour(s)
Maximum inflow of 13.934 ft³/s occurs at 0 Hours 42 Minutes
Maximum outflow of 13.633 ft³/s occurs at 0 Hours 45 Minutes

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – STAGE STORAGE TABLE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
 Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
 Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
 Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
 Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Total Site Stage Storage

Description : Miami-Dade 25 Year 6 Hour Storm

STAGE (ft)	VOLUME (Ac-ft)	STAGE (ft)	VOLUME (Ac-ft)	STAGE (ft)	VOLUME (Ac-ft)
2.700	0.0000	8.500	0.1883		
2.701	0.0000	9.000	0.2717		
2.800	0.0028	9.500	0.5821		
3.150	0.0178	10.000	1.0181		
3.875	0.0525				
4.600	0.0888				
5.325	0.1241				
5.700	0.1404				
5.800	0.1431				
6.050	0.1496				
6.775	0.1687				
7.499	0.1883				
7.500	0.1883				
7.501	0.1883				
7.600	0.1883				
7.700	0.1883				
7.800	0.1883				
7.900	0.1883				
7.999	0.1883				
8.000	0.1883				
8.001	0.1883				

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – STAGE DISCHARGE TABLE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
 Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
 Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
 Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
 Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Total Site Stage Discharge

Description : Miami-Dade 25 Year 6 Hour Storm

STAGE (ft)	FLOW (ft ³ /s)	STAGE (ft)	FLOW (ft ³ /s)	STAGE (ft)	FLOW (ft ³ /s)
2.700	0.0000	8.500	13.5928		
2.701	0.0010	9.000	16.1526		
2.800	0.1050	9.500	18.3603		
3.150	0.4776	10.000	20.3612		
3.875	1.2747				
4.600	2.1059				
5.325	2.9712				
5.700	3.4321				
5.800	3.5566				
6.050	3.8706				
6.775	4.8040				
7.499	5.7701				
7.500	5.7715				
7.501	5.7731				
7.600	6.2016				
7.700	6.8757				
7.800	7.7085				
7.900	8.6697				
7.999	9.7304				
8.000	9.7417				
8.001	9.7498				

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – MASS INFLOW-OUTFLOW TABLE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
 Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
 Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
 Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
 Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Mass Curve

Description : Miami-Dade 25 Year 6 Hour Storm

TIME (Hours)	INFLOW VOLUME (Ac-ft)	OUTFLOW VOLUME (Ac-ft)	DIFFERENCE VOLUME (Ac-ft)
1:45	0.143	0.069	0.074
1:46	0.147	0.072	0.076
1:47	0.152	0.074	0.078
1:48	0.157	0.077	0.080
1:49	0.162	0.080	0.082
1:50	0.167	0.082	0.085
1:51	0.172	0.085	0.087
1:52	0.178	0.088	0.089
1:53	0.183	0.091	0.092
1:54	0.189	0.094	0.095
1:55	0.195	0.097	0.097
1:56	0.201	0.101	0.100
1:57	0.207	0.104	0.103
1:58	0.213	0.108	0.105
1:59	0.219	0.111	0.108
2:00	0.226	0.115	0.111
2:01	0.232	0.118	0.114
2:02	0.239	0.122	0.117
2:03	0.246	0.126	0.120
2:04	0.253	0.130	0.123
2:05	0.261	0.135	0.126

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – STAGE DURATION TABLE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
 Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
 Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
 Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
 Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Stage Duration

Description : Miami-Dade 25 Year 6 Hour Storm

TIME (Hours)	STAGE (ft)	TIME (Hours)	STAGE (ft)	TIME (Hours)	STAGE (ft)
0:00	2.700	0:21	2.701	0:42	2.797
0:01	2.700	0:22	2.701	0:43	2.805
0:02	2.700	0:23	2.702	0:44	2.813
0:03	2.700	0:24	2.703	0:45	2.822
0:04	2.700	0:25	2.704	0:46	2.832
0:05	2.700	0:26	2.706	0:47	2.842
0:06	2.700	0:27	2.708	0:48	2.853
0:07	2.700	0:28	2.710	0:49	2.865
0:08	2.700	0:29	2.713	0:50	2.877
0:09	2.700	0:30	2.716	0:51	2.890
0:10	2.700	0:31	2.720	0:52	2.904
0:11	2.700	0:32	2.724	0:53	2.919
0:12	2.700	0:33	2.728	0:54	2.935
0:13	2.700	0:34	2.733	0:55	2.951
0:14	2.700	0:35	2.739	0:56	2.968
0:15	2.700	0:36	2.745	0:57	2.986
0:16	2.700	0:37	2.752	0:58	3.005
0:17	2.700	0:38	2.759	0:59	3.024
0:18	2.700	0:39	2.767	1:00	3.045
0:19	2.700	0:40	2.776	1:01	3.066
0:20	2.700	0:41	2.786	1:02	3.088

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – INFLOW HYDROGRAPH TABLE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
 Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
 Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
 Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
 Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Inflow Duration

Description : Miami-Dade 25 Year 6 Hour Storm

TIME (Hours)	FLOW (ft ³ /s)	TIME (Hours)	FLOW (ft ³ /s)	TIME (Hours)	FLOW (ft ³ /s)
0:00	0.000	0:21	0.009	0:42	0.318
0:01	0.000	0:22	0.013	0:43	0.347
0:02	0.000	0:23	0.018	0:44	0.377
0:03	0.000	0:24	0.025	0:45	0.407
0:04	0.000	0:25	0.032	0:46	0.439
0:05	0.000	0:26	0.041	0:47	0.471
0:06	0.000	0:27	0.050	0:48	0.505
0:07	0.000	0:28	0.060	0:49	0.540
0:08	0.000	0:29	0.071	0:50	0.576
0:09	0.000	0:30	0.082	0:51	0.614
0:10	0.000	0:31	0.094	0:52	0.652
0:11	0.000	0:32	0.107	0:53	0.692
0:12	0.000	0:33	0.122	0:54	0.733
0:13	0.000	0:34	0.137	0:55	0.775
0:14	0.000	0:35	0.155	0:56	0.818
0:15	0.000	0:36	0.174	0:57	0.861
0:16	0.000	0:37	0.194	0:58	0.906
0:17	0.000	0:38	0.216	0:59	0.951
0:18	0.001	0:39	0.240	1:00	0.997
0:19	0.003	0:40	0.265	1:01	1.044
0:20	0.005	0:41	0.291	1:02	1.091

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – OUTFLOW HYDROGRAPH TABLE

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
 Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
 Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
 Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
 Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Outflow Duration

Description : Miami-Dade 25 Year 6 Hour Storm

TIME (Hours)	FLOW (ft ³ /s)	TIME (Hours)	FLOW (ft ³ /s)	TIME (Hours)	FLOW (ft ³ /s)
0:00	0.000	0:21	0.001	0:42	0.101
0:01	0.000	0:22	0.001	0:43	0.111
0:02	0.000	0:23	0.002	0:44	0.119
0:03	0.000	0:24	0.003	0:45	0.129
0:04	0.000	0:25	0.005	0:46	0.139
0:05	0.000	0:26	0.006	0:47	0.150
0:06	0.000	0:27	0.008	0:48	0.162
0:07	0.000	0:28	0.011	0:49	0.174
0:08	0.000	0:29	0.014	0:50	0.187
0:09	0.000	0:30	0.017	0:51	0.201
0:10	0.000	0:31	0.021	0:52	0.216
0:11	0.000	0:32	0.025	0:53	0.232
0:12	0.000	0:33	0.030	0:54	0.248
0:13	0.000	0:34	0.035	0:55	0.266
0:14	0.000	0:35	0.041	0:56	0.284
0:15	0.000	0:36	0.047	0:57	0.303
0:16	0.000	0:37	0.054	0:58	0.323
0:17	0.000	0:38	0.062	0:59	0.344
0:18	0.000	0:39	0.071	1:00	0.365
0:19	0.000	0:40	0.080	1:01	0.388
0:20	0.000	0:41	0.090	1:02	0.411

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ROUTING ANALYSIS SAMPLE OUTPUT – INFLOW, OUTFLOW HYDROGRAPH

Project Number : SAMPLE PROBLEM
Project Location : MIAMI DADE COUNTY
Company Name : FLORIDA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
Client Name : CITY OF MIAMI
Designer Name : F.M.

SCS-FLOOD HYDROGRAPH METHOD - Inflow-Outflow Duration

Description : Miami-Dade 25 Year 6 Hour Storm

TIME (Hours)	INFLOW (ft ³ /s)	OUTFLOW (ft ³ /s)	STORAGE VOLUME (Ac-ft)	STAGE (ft)
0:00	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:01	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:02	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:03	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:04	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:05	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:06	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:07	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:08	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:09	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:10	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:11	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:12	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:13	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:14	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:15	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:16	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:17	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:18	0.001	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:19	0.003	0.000	0.000	2.700
0:20	0.005	0.000	0.000	2.700

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